

A NOTE ON A GENERALIZATION OF FUNDAMENTAL GAPS IN NUMERICAL SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract

Let S be a numerical semigroup. A positive integer n is a fundamental gap of S if $n \notin S$ whereas $kn \in S$ for each integer $k > 1$. We call a positive integer n a fundamental gap of order λ , $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, if $kn \notin S$ for each $k \in \{1, \dots, \lambda\}$ and $kn \in S$ for each integer $k > \lambda$. We investigate the set $\text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ of fundamental gaps of S of order λ when S has embedding dimension two.

1. Introduction

By $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and \mathbb{N} we mean the set of non-negative integers and the set of positive integers, respectively. A numerical semigroup is a subset S of $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ that is closed under addition, $0 \in S$ and $\mathbb{N} \setminus S$ is a finite set. If $a_1, \dots, a_k \in \mathbb{N}$, we set

$$\langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle = \left\{ a_1x_1 + \dots + a_kx_k : x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \right\}.$$

Then $\langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle$ is a numerical semigroup if and only if $\gcd(a_1, \dots, a_k) = 1$.

The set $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$ is called a system of generators of the semigroup $S = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle$. For a semigroup S , A is a minimal system of generators if A generates S and no proper subset of A generates S . Every numerical semigroup has a unique minimal system of generators. This system of generators is finite, and the cardinality of this minimal system of generators is called the embedding dimension of S , and is denoted by $e(S)$.

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Given a numerical semigroup S , we define the set $G(S)$ of gaps of S to be $\mathbb{N} \setminus S$. An element $n \in G(S)$, following Rosales et al [4], is defined to be a fundamental gap if $kn \in S$ for each $k > 1$. It is easy to see that the set of fundamental gaps $FG(S)$ determines the numerical semigroup S uniquely, as any element in $G(S)$ is just a divisor of some fundamental gap. Fundamental gaps are a special case of special gaps. Special gaps are of interest, as they help in solving the problem of oversemigroups of a given numerical semigroup. The set $FG(S)$ of all fundamental gaps of S has been determined by Rosales [2] in the case where S has embedding dimension 2. Rosales and García-Sánchez [3] provide a comprehensive introduction to the study of Numerical Semigroups.

In this note, we extend the notion of fundamental gaps to the notion of fundamental gaps of an arbitrary order λ , $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, and determine the set $FG(S, \lambda)$ of all fundamental gaps of order λ where the embedding dimension of S is 2, and derive $FG(S)$ as a special case. Whereas the set of fundamental gaps, $FG(S)$, uniquely determine the semigroup, in general, the set of fundamental gaps of order λ , $FG(S, \lambda)$, for $\lambda > 1$ do not usually determine the semigroup. For instance, taking two numerical semigroups S and T , neither of which is an ordinary semigroup, with $F(S) = F(T)$, it is easy to check that $FG(S, F(S)) = FG(T, F(T)) = \emptyset$. In fact, if $\lambda > F(S)$, then $FG(S, \lambda) = \emptyset$. In particular, when $\lambda > 1$, the set $FG(S, \lambda)$ does not provide a way to test for membership of the numerical semigroup.

For a numerical semigroup S and a positive integer n , the set $\frac{S}{n}$ is given by $\{m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} : mn \in S\}$. It is well known that every proportionally modular numerical semigroup is of the form $\frac{\langle a, b \rangle}{n}$ for some positive integers a, b, n where $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ (see [5]). Also, note that

$$FG(S, \lambda) = \left(\bigcap_{k>\lambda} \frac{S}{k} \right) \setminus (S \cup \frac{S}{2} \cup \dots \cup \frac{S}{\lambda}).$$

Hence it is not surprising to see that modular inequalities appear in Theorem 1.

2. Main Result

Given a numerical semigroup S and a positive integer λ , in this section, we define a fundamental gap of S of order λ , and explicitly determine the set of fundamental gaps of S of order λ in the case where S has embedding dimension 2.

Definition 1. Let S be a numerical semigroup and let $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$. We say that a positive integer n is a *Fundamental Gap of Order λ* if $kn \notin S$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$ and $kn \in S$ for $k > \lambda$. We denote the set of all fundamental gaps of S of order λ by $FG(S, \lambda)$.

Lemma 1. *Let S be a numerical semigroup and let $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $n \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $kn \notin S$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$ and $kn \in S$ for $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1$.*

Proof. Suppose n is a positive integer such that $kn \in S$ for $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1$. Choose any $k > \lambda$, and write $k = q(\lambda + 1) + r$, with $q \geq 1$ and $0 \leq r \leq \lambda$. Then $kn = ((q - 1)(\lambda + 1) + (\lambda + r + 1))n \in S$, since $(\lambda + 1)n \in S$ and $(\lambda + r + 1)n \in S$. This proves the sufficiency. The necessity is obvious. \square

The Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_n of order n is the ascending sequence of rational numbers $\frac{h}{k}$ between 0 and 1 with $\text{gcd}(h, k) = 1$ and $1 \leq k \leq n$. Farey sequences are fascinating in their own right, and useful in the study of Diophantine Approximations. The following results are useful in the explicit determination of $\text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ when S has embedding dimension 2.

Proposition 1. ([1, Theorem 5.8, p. 44])

The term immediately succeeding $\frac{a}{b}$ in the Farey sequence \mathcal{F}_n of order n is given by $\frac{c}{d}$, where

$$bc - ad = 1 \text{ and } 0 \leq n - b < d \leq n.$$

Lemma 2. *Let $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$. Then*

$$\left[\frac{1}{\lambda}, \frac{2\lambda-1}{2\lambda} \right) = \bigcup_{1 \leq c < k \leq \lambda} \left[\frac{c}{k}, \frac{\left\lceil \frac{\lambda+1}{k} \right\rceil c+1}{\left\lfloor \frac{\lambda+1}{k} \right\rfloor k} \right).$$

Proof. Throughout the proof, let $m(k) = \left\lceil \frac{\lambda+1}{k} \right\rceil$. Let

$$X = \left[\frac{1}{\lambda}, \frac{2\lambda-1}{2\lambda} \right) \text{ and } Y = \bigcup_{1 \leq c < k \leq \lambda} \left[\frac{c}{k}, \frac{m(k) \cdot c+1}{m(k) \cdot k} \right).$$

Let $x \in X$. Then $x \in \left[\frac{u}{v}, \frac{u'}{v'} \right)$, where $\frac{u}{v}, \frac{u'}{v'}$ are consecutive terms in $\mathcal{F}_\lambda \setminus \{0, 1\}$, or $x \in \left[\frac{\lambda-1}{\lambda}, \frac{2\lambda-1}{2\lambda} \right)$.

In the first case, choose $c = u, k = v$. By Proposition 1, $0 \leq \lambda - k < v' \leq \lambda$, and so $\lambda + 1 \leq k + v' \leq kv'$. Hence $m(k) \cdot (uv' - u'v) = m(k) \leq v'$, and so $\frac{u'}{v'} \leq \frac{m(k) \cdot c+1}{m(k) \cdot k}$.

In the second case, choose $c = \lambda - 1, k = \lambda$, and so $m(k) = 2$.

Hence $x \in \left[\frac{c}{k}, \frac{m(k) \cdot c+1}{m(k) \cdot k} \right)$ in each case, and so $X \subseteq Y$.

To show $X = Y$, it now suffices to show

$$\begin{aligned} \min \left\{ \frac{c}{k} : 1 \leq c < k, 2 \leq k \leq \lambda \right\} &= \frac{1}{\lambda}, \\ \max \left\{ \frac{m(k) \cdot c+1}{m(k) \cdot k} : 1 \leq c < k \leq \lambda \right\} &= \frac{2\lambda-1}{2\lambda}. \end{aligned}$$

The first claim is obvious. To prove the second claim, first note that $m(k) \geq 2 \geq 1 + \frac{k}{2\lambda-k} = \frac{2\lambda}{2\lambda-k}$. Hence $c \leq k - 1 \leq \frac{(2\lambda-1)m(k) \cdot k - 2\lambda}{2\lambda m(k)}$, so that $\frac{m(k) \cdot c+1}{m(k) \cdot k} \leq \frac{2\lambda-1}{2\lambda}$. To show the bound is attained, choose $c = \lambda - 1, k = \lambda$, and so $m(k) = 2$. This completes the claim that $X = Y$. \square

Our main result is the determination of $FG(S, \lambda)$ when $S = \langle a, b \rangle$, $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Corresponding to each nonzero element n in a numerical semigroup S , we define the Apéry set $Ap(S, n)$ of S . Apéry sets are essential tools in the study of numerical semigroups.

Definition 2. Let S be a numerical semigroup and let $n \in S \setminus \{0\}$. The Apéry set of S corresponding to n is defined as

$$Ap(S, n) = \{s \in S : s - n \notin S\}.$$

Theorem 1. Let $S = \langle a, b \rangle$, where $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. The set of Fundamental Gaps of order λ is given by

$$FG(S, \lambda) = A \cup B \cup C \cup D \cup E,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \left\{ bs - ar : \frac{(\lambda-1)b}{\lambda} < r \leq \frac{\lambda b}{\lambda+1}, \frac{2\lambda a}{2\lambda+1} \leq s \leq a - 1 \right\}, \\ B &= \left\{ bs - ar : \frac{(\lambda-1)b}{\lambda} < r \leq \frac{(2\lambda-1)b}{2\lambda+1}, \frac{(2\lambda-1)a}{2\lambda} \leq s < \frac{2\lambda a}{2\lambda+1} \right\}, \\ C &= \left\{ bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda+1}, s = \frac{a}{\lambda+1} \right\}, \\ D &= \left\{ bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda}, \frac{a}{\lambda+1} < s < \frac{a}{\lambda}, 0 < a \bmod s \leq \frac{s}{2} \right\}, \\ E &= \left\{ bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda+1}, \frac{a}{\lambda+1} < s < \frac{a}{\lambda}, a \bmod s > \frac{s}{2} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. For $S = \langle a, b \rangle$, note that $Ap(S, a) = \{bs : 0 \leq s \leq a - 1\}$. Thus, any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ is of the form $bs - ar$ with $0 \leq s \leq a - 1$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}$; see [3, Lemma 2.4, p. 8], for instance. Hence, $n \in S$ if and only if $r \leq 0$. Therefore, $n \notin S$ if and only if $r > 0$. Therefore $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus S$ if and only if $1 \leq s \leq a - 1$ and $1 \leq r < \frac{bs}{a}$.

Recall that n is a fundamental gap of order λ if and only if $kn \notin S$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$ and $kn \in S$ for $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1$. The latter is equivalent to

$$k(bs - ar) < b(ks \bmod a) \quad \text{if } 1 \leq k \leq \lambda; \tag{1}$$

$$k(bs - ar) \geq b(ks \bmod a) \quad \text{if } \lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1. \tag{2}$$

Fix $s \in \{1, \dots, a - 1\}$, and write $a = qs + \rho$, $0 \leq \rho < s$.

Case I. ($q < \lambda$)

With $s = a - t$, $t \geq 1$, $q < \lambda$ is equivalent to $t < \frac{(\lambda-1)a}{\lambda}$. We consider three subcases:

(i) $1 \leq t \leq \frac{a}{2\lambda+1}$; (ii) $\frac{a}{2\lambda+1} < t \leq \frac{a}{2\lambda}$; (iii) $\frac{a}{2\lambda} < t < \frac{(\lambda-1)a}{\lambda}$.

In subcases (i) and (ii), if $1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda$, then $ks \equiv -kt \pmod{a}$ and $1 \leq kt \leq a$. Therefore $ks \bmod a = a - kt$.

In subcase (i), if $k = 2\lambda + 1$, then $ks \equiv -kt \pmod{a}$ and $2\lambda + 1 \leq (2\lambda + 1)t \leq a$. Therefore $ks \pmod{a} = a - kt$.

In subcase (ii), if $k = 2\lambda + 1$, then $ks \equiv -kt \pmod{a}$ and $a < (2\lambda + 1)t \leq \frac{(2\lambda+1)a}{2\lambda} < 2a$. Therefore $ks \pmod{a} = 2a - kt$.

In subcase (i), inequality (1) reduces to $k(b(a-t) - ar) < b(a-kt)$, $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$, and inequality (2) reduces to $k(b(a-t) - ar) \geq b(a-kt)$, $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1$. Hence $n \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $r > \frac{(k-1)b}{k}$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$ and $r \leq \frac{(k-1)b}{k}$ for $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1$. Therefore $n \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if

$$\max \left\{ \frac{(k-1)b}{k} : 1 \leq k \leq \lambda \right\} = \frac{(\lambda-1)b}{\lambda} < r \leq \min \left\{ \frac{(k-1)b}{k} : \lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1 \right\} = \frac{\lambda b}{\lambda + 1}.$$

This leads to $n \in A$.

In subcase (ii), inequality (1) reduces to $k(b(a-t) - ar) < b(a-kt)$, $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$, and inequality (2) reduces to $k(b(a-t) - ar) \geq b(a-kt)$, $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda$ and to $k(b(a-t) - ar) \geq b(2a - kt)$ for $k = 2\lambda + 1$. Hence $n \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $r > \frac{(k-1)b}{k}$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$, $r \leq \frac{(k-1)b}{k}$ for $\lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda$ and $r \leq \frac{(2\lambda-1)b}{2\lambda+1}$. Therefore $n \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \max \left\{ \frac{(k-1)b}{k} : 1 \leq k \leq \lambda \right\} &= \frac{(\lambda-1)b}{\lambda} \\ &< r \\ &\leq \min \left\{ \min \left\{ \frac{(k-1)b}{k} : \lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda \right\}, \frac{(2\lambda-1)b}{2\lambda+1} \right\} \\ &= \frac{(2\lambda-1)b}{2\lambda+1}. \end{aligned}$$

This leads to $n \in B$.

We claim that $n \notin \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ in subcase (iii). Using $ks - (ks \pmod{a}) = \lfloor \frac{ks}{a} \rfloor a$ in inequality (1) yields

$$b \lfloor \frac{ks}{a} \rfloor < kr, \quad 1 \leq k \leq \lambda, \tag{3}$$

and inequality (2) yields

$$b \lfloor \frac{ks}{a} \rfloor \geq kr, \quad \lambda + 1 \leq k \leq 2\lambda + 1. \tag{4}$$

In subcase (iii), we have $n = bs - ar$, with $\frac{a}{\lambda} < s < \frac{(2\lambda-1)a}{2\lambda}$. Hence $\frac{s}{a} \in X$, so $\frac{s}{a} \in \left[\frac{c}{k}, \frac{m(k) \cdot c + 1}{m(k) \cdot k} \right)$ with $1 \leq c < k \leq \lambda$ and $\lambda + 1 \leq m(k) \cdot k \leq 2\lambda + 1$, by Lemma 2. Since $1 \leq k \leq \lambda$, using $\frac{c}{k} \leq \frac{s}{a}$, or the equivalent $c \leq \frac{ks}{a}$ in inequality (3) we get $bc < kr$. Since $\lambda + 1 \leq m(k) \cdot k \leq 2\lambda + 1$, using $\frac{s}{a} < \frac{m(k) \cdot c + 1}{m(k) \cdot k}$ in inequality (4) we get $m(k) \cdot kr \leq m(k) \cdot bc$, or that $kr \leq bc$. Thus, there is no r corresponding to s covered by the subcase (iii). Hence $n \notin \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ in subcase (iii).

Case II. ($q \geq \lambda$)

If $q > \lambda$, then inequality (2) fails to hold for $k = \lambda + 1$ since $(\lambda + 1)s \bmod a = (\lambda + 1)s$ and $(\lambda + 1)(bs - ar) < b(\lambda + 1)s$ unless $\rho = 0$ and $q = \lambda + 1$. For $\rho = 0$ and $q = \lambda + 1$, inequality (2) holds for $k = \lambda + 1$ because $(\lambda + 1)s \bmod a = 0$.

For the rest of this proof, we assume $q = \lambda$, and when $\rho = 0$ we need to consider the additional $q = \lambda + 1$.

Subcase (i). ($\rho = 0$)

If $q = \lambda$, then inequality (1) fails to hold for $k = q$ since $qs \bmod a = 0$.

Suppose $q = \lambda + 1$. Then inequality (1) reduces to $k(bs - ar) < b(ks)$, and inequality (2) reduces to $k(bs - ar) \geq b(ks - a)$, since $a = (\lambda + 1)s < (2\lambda + 1)s < 2a$. It is evident that inequality (1) holds, and that inequality (2) holds if and only if $r \leq \frac{b}{k}$ holds for $k \in \{\lambda + 1, \dots, 2\lambda + 1\}$. Hence $bs - ar \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $s = \frac{a}{\lambda + 1}$ and $1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda + 1}$. This leads to $n \in C$.

Subcase (ii). ($0 < \rho \leq \frac{s}{2}$)

Suppose $q = \lambda$. Then inequality (1) reduces to $k(bs - ar) < b(ks)$, and this evidently holds. Since $a < (\lambda + 1)s \leq 2\lambda s < 2a \leq (2\lambda + 1)s < 3a$, inequality (2) reduces to $k(bs - ar) \geq b(ks - a)$ for $k \in \{\lambda + 1, \dots, 2\lambda\}$ and to $k(bs - ar) \geq b(ks - 2a)$ for $k = 2\lambda + 1$. Hence inequality (2) holds if and only if $r \leq \frac{b}{k}$ holds for $k \in \{\lambda + 1, \dots, 2\lambda\}$ and $r \leq \frac{2b}{k}$ holds for $k = 2\lambda + 1$. Hence $bs - ar \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $\lambda = q = \lfloor \frac{a}{s} \rfloor$ and $1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda}$. This leads to $n \in D$.

Subcase (iii). ($\rho > \frac{s}{2}$)

Suppose $q = \lambda$. Then inequality (1) reduces to $k(bs - ar) < b(ks)$, and inequality (2) reduces to $k(bs - ar) \geq b(ks - a)$, since $a < (\lambda + 1)s < (2\lambda + 1)s < 2a$. It is evident that inequality (1) holds, and that inequality (2) holds if and only if $r \leq \frac{b}{k}$ holds for $k \in \{\lambda + 1, \dots, 2\lambda + 1\}$. Hence $bs - ar \in \text{FG}(S, \lambda)$ if and only if $\lambda = q = \lfloor \frac{a}{s} \rfloor$ and $1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2\lambda + 1}$. This leads to $n \in E$. □

Corollary 1. Let $S = \langle a, b \rangle$, where $\text{gcd}(a, b) = 1$. The set of Fundamental Gaps is given by

$$\text{FG}(S) = \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{3}, \frac{a}{2} \leq s < \frac{2a}{3}\} \cup \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2}, \frac{2a}{3} \leq s \leq a - 1\}.$$

Proof. For $\lambda = 1$, Theorem 1 gives

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \{bs - ar : 0 < r \leq \frac{b}{2}, \frac{2a}{3} \leq s \leq a - 1\}, \\ B &= \{bs - ar : 0 < r \leq \frac{b}{3}, \frac{a}{2} \leq s < \frac{2a}{3}\}, \\ C &= \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{3}, s = \frac{a}{2}\}, \\ D &= \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2}, \frac{a}{2} < s < a, 0 < a \bmod s \leq \frac{s}{2}\}, \\ E &= \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{3}, \frac{a}{2} < s < a, a \bmod s > \frac{s}{2}\}. \end{aligned}$$

When $\frac{a}{2} < s < a$, $\lfloor \frac{a}{s} \rfloor = 1$, and so $a \bmod s = a - \lfloor \frac{a}{s} \rfloor s = a - s$. Hence

$$C \cup E = \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{3}, \frac{a}{2} \leq s < a, a \bmod s > \frac{s}{2}\} = B,$$

$$D = \{bs - ar : 1 \leq r \leq \frac{b}{2}, \frac{2a}{3} \leq s < a\} = A.$$

Therefore $FG(S) = A \cup B$. □

We illustrate Theorem 1 with the following example.

Example 1. For $S = \langle 13, 31 \rangle$, we get

λ	$FG(S, \lambda)$
1	84, 87, 97, 100, 110, 113, 115, 118, 123, 126, 128, 131, 136, 139, 141, 144, 146, 149, 152, 154, 157, 159, 162, 165, 167, 170, 172, 175, 177, 178, 180, 183, 185, 188, 190, 191, 193, 196, 198, 201, 203, 204, 206, 209, 211, 214, 216, 219, 222, 224, 227, 229, 232, 235, 237, 240, 242, 245, 250, 253, 255, 258, 263, 266, 268, 271, 276, 281, 284, 289, 294, 297, 302, 307, 315, 320, 328, 333, 346, 359
2	76, 77, 81, 89, 90, 94, 95, 102, 103, 107, 108, 112, 116, 120, 121, 125, 129, 133, 134, 138, 142, 147, 151, 160, 164, 173
3	55, 59, 68, 72, 73, 85, 86, 98, 99, 111
4	54, 60, 67, 80
5	47
6	34, 36, 49
$[7, 11]$	\emptyset
12	18
≥ 13	\emptyset

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